

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N. 723386

Contact us
SIMUSAFE.eu

Project contacts:

Mrs. María Teresa Cobo
maite.cobo@itcl.es

Mr. Marteyn van Gasteren
marteyn.vangasteren@itcl.es

NEWSLETTER #1

Project Partners

• APTIV •

MÅLARDALEN UNIVERSITY
SWEDEN

SCHUHFRIED
passion for psychology

UNIVERSITÀ
CATTOLICA
del Sacro Cuore

January 2018

The consortium met outside of Paris at an event hosted by IFSTTAR. The partners made progress on the Naturalistic phase of the project focusing in data collection (WP2) and sensorization (and sensorisation) (WP4).

The Consortium meeting started with an agenda consisting of 10 Work Package Progress Meetings (WPPM), one for each WP, Scientific and Ethical Committees and Exploitation Board presentations, and additionally 8 afternoon workshops on specific topics.

During this partner meeting, the consortium accomplished an advanced definition of the data collection for each of the four actors, of paramount importance for cycle progress.

Partner Dissemination

AIPSS, the Associazione Italiana Professionisti per la Sicurezza Stradale published an article describing the SIMUSAFE project in *leStrade* (Aeroporti Autostrade Ferrovie). *leStrade* is a monthly, technical magazine for industry focused on transportation infrastructure including construction and maintenance.

108
Simulatore per la sicurezza
Via a SIMUSAFE con la pre-selezione di 15 volontari per un test di guida naturalistica

AVVISO
SELEZIONE DI N. 15 VOLONTARI PER IL PROGETTO EUROPEO DI RICERCA SIMUSAFE

1. Kick-off del progetto SIMUSAFE

2. Avviso di pre-selezione dei volontari, scaricabile dal sito web AIPSS

ASSOCIAZIONE AIPSS
0-9/2017 leStrade

Cloud-based Data Analytics on Human Factor Measurement to Improve Safer Transport

Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Shahina Begum, Carlos Alberto Catalina, Lior Limor, Bertil Hans, Gianluca Di Florio

Summary
Improving safer transport includes individual and collective behavioural aspects and their interaction. A system that can monitor and evaluate the human cognitive and physical capacities based on human factor measurement is often beneficial to improve safety in driving condition. However, analysis and evaluation of human factor measurement i.e. demographics, behaviour and physiology in real-time is challenging. This paper presents a methodology for cloud-based data analysis, categorization and metrics correlation in real-time through a H2020 project called SimuSafe. Initial implementation of this methodology shows a step-by-step approach which can handle huge amount of data with variation and verify in the cloud.

System Overview

Method and Approach

Data Analytics for SimuSafe

- Phase 1: Information fusion and data abstraction**
 - Artifact handling
 - Service/data fusion
 - Feature extraction
 - Feature selection and optimization
- Phase 2: Data mining and knowledge discovery**
 - Anomaly detection
 - Knowledge mining
 - Rules extraction
 - Pattern recognition
 - Regression
- Phase 3: Learning, reasoning and model creation**
 - Knowledge engineering
 - Learning and reasoning
 - Deep Learning
 - Decision support

Conclusion
The proposed approach shows the possibility to handle, process and analyze the Demographics, Behavioural and Physiological data in Big data context. IBM Bluemix cloud platform is used with three parallel nodes where analytics phases are implemented. The phases are:
1) Information fusion and data abstraction,
2) Data mining and knowledge discovery and
3) Learning, reasoning and model creation.

Logos: Mälardalen University Sweden, ESS-H, European Commission, SIMUSAFE

Mälardalen University (MDH) presented a poster at 4th EAI International Conference on IoT Technologies for HealthCare. HealthyIoT (2017) an international scientific event series "dedicated to Internet of Things and Healthcare. The Internet of Things, as a set of existing and emerging technologies, notions and services, can provide many solutions to delivery of electronic healthcare, patient care and medical data management."

Upcoming Conferences

June

MobiSys 2018

The 16th ACM International Conference on Mobile Systems, Applications, and Services

IV'18

The 2018 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium

July

AHFE 2018

9th International Conference on Applied Human Factors and Ergonomics

EMBC18

40th International Engineering in Medicine and Biology Conference

August

MobiSys 2018

The 16th ACM International Conference on Mobile Systems, Applications, and Services

September

AAIA'18

13th International Symposium Advances in Artificial Intelligence and Applications

DSC2018

17th Driving Simulation & Virtual Reality Conference & Exhibition

DDI2018

The 6th International Conference on Driver Distraction and Inattention

NADS-1 at The University of Iowa

 THE UNIVERSITY OF IOWA

IOWA STATE
UNIVERSITY

InterchangeSE scenario at Iowa State University
(reactor.ctr.e.iastate.edu)

SimuSafe twins with 2 US-funded projects

SimuSafe has been invited to set up a twinning activity with two US-funded research projects to collaborate and explore synergies concerning simulator technologies for road safety. Currently the coordinators of the three projects are in the initial contact stage to determine the scope of this cooperation.

The University of Iowa, site of the National Advanced Driving Simulator (NADS), leads the project "Developing Connected Simulation to Study Interactions between Drivers, Pedestrians, and Bicyclists". Another university from the same state, Iowa State University, coordinates the project "Interchange SE: A Federated Multimodal Simulation Environment for Studying Interactions between Different Modes of Travel". Both projects conduct research on multi-actor simulation of road users. "Multi-actor simulations are a key technology used and developed within the simulations of the SimuSafe research cycles, which makes the link between these three projects very promising. Apart from on-line meetings for mutual updates and technical discussion, we plan for yearly face-to-face meetings to showcase progress," as Marteyn van Gasteren points out, SimuSafe's project coordinator from ITCL Institute of Technology.

The European Commission (EC) and the United States Department of Transportation (USDOT), flagged transport as one of four priority research areas for transatlantic science and technology cooperation; the other three being Marine & Arctic Research, (NMP, and Health. Part of this cooperation is the twinning programme, with the objective to encourage research collaboration between mobility-related projects of similar topics in Europe and the United States, on the basis of mutual interest.

Data protection: A brief introduction to the GDPR

Over the last couple of months, you may have received many email notifications about changing terms of service. This was due to a new data protection law, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which went into effect in May of 2018. The European Parliament, the council of the European Union, and the European Commission “intend [the GDPR] to strengthen and unify data protection for all individuals within the EU”.*

The Regulation’s primary objectives are:

- The protection of fundamental rights and freedoms of individual persons with regard to processing of personal data; and
- The protection of the principle of free movement of personal data within the EU.*

Figure 1: *Examples of Personal Data*, from Coventry University's **IPU GDPR Briefing for Research**. April 2018.

As researchers, we must be careful with the personal data which we may collect during the course of our research activities. According to the GDPR, personal data is:

...any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.*

GDPR broadens the categories of personal data and includes more than just someone's name or identification numbers. Under GDPR, personal data also includes a person's credit history, the license plate of their vehicle and even trade union membership (figure 1).

As researchers, we need to consider how and what personal data we collect, process, transfer, and store. We must only collect data which is necessary for our research purposes, and may not keep this data for longer than necessary. Additionally, all data must be anonymized to ensure it is not traced back to individuals.

Further information can be found at the European Commission's data protection site.

* Coventry University, *Data Protection—the GDPR: Summary*. 2018

SIMUSAFE welcomes a new collaborator

We are proud to have the creator and manufacturer of the Vienna Test System (VTS) join SIMUSAFE as a collaborator. Originally a pioneer of digital testing, SCHUHFRIED is now an acknowledged expert in this field. More than 13 million tests are administered using the Vienna Test System each year for neuropsychological and clinical purposes, but above all for the assessment of fitness to drive. Specifically, the agreement between SCHUHFRIED and SIMUSAFE will involve the DRIVESTA fitness-to-drive test which considers the measurement of driver skills such as reaction time, perception, attention, and risk perception.

The agreement between SIMUSAFE and SCHUHFRIED is also an interesting stimulus for research, both for participating in the project of different nations and cultures, as well as for the interest in different actors on the road. The objectives of SIMUSAFE include gathering data not only about vehicle drivers but also motorcyclists, cyclists and pedestrians. Analyzing and comparing the VTS performance of different users can be an interesting contribution to this project. Furthermore, the SIMUSAFE results may contribute towards further improving the Vienna Test is possible further positive impact we can achieve together.

Upcoming Workshop: Are Novice Drivers at Risk? Graduated driving license, a challenge for safety.

UCSC's Department of Psychology, in conjunction with the SIMUSAFE partners EFA and AIPSS held an International Workshop on 26 June, 2018 in Milano, Italy. This workshop focused on Graduated Driving Licenses examining topics such as the challenges of new technologies, training comparisons, and the effects of fines on novice drivers. Lessons learned from other EU countries were also discussed.

Workshop announcements in Italian and English

DIPARTIMENTO DI PSICOLOGIA

NEOPATENTATI: CATEGORIA A RISCHIO?

La patente progressiva sfida formativa per la sicurezza

Conseguire la patente è una tappa importante per l'autonomia, tuttavia i dati sull'incidentalità rivelano come fascia critica quella dai 18 ai 25 anni, età che costituisce per la maggioranza dei patentati il momento in cui le competenze vengono messe alla prova mediante l'esperienza diretta sulla strada. Per questo in alcuni paesi è stata adottata il modello della formazione progressiva che accompagna il neopatentato nei primi anni di guida, verificando abilità e compatibilità con le norme prima di confermare l'acquisizione della patente. Obiettivo del seminario è approfondire questa tematica esplorando a livello internazionale le valenze formative e le ricadute sulla sicurezza.

Ore 09.30
Accoglienza e registrazione

Ore 10.00
Misure preventive previste dalla legislazione italiana nei primi tre anni di guida
S. DONDOLINI
Direzione Generale Motorizzazione, Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti

Ore 10.20
Confronto critico tra i diversi sistemi di formazione dei novice driver in Europa
M. PICARDI
1President, EFA - European Driving School Association

Ore 10.40
Second phase driver training in Austria Background and evaluation
G. BARIL
Traffic psychologist
Director of the Institute for Traffic Psychology, Austria

Ore 11.00
L'acquisizione della patente come processo a fasi: il sistema svizzero
V. BORGIO
Maestro Conduttore, Svizzera
G. GALMARINI
Psicologo del Traffico, Svizzera

Ore 11.30
Coffee Break

Ore 12.00
Le sfide delle nuove tecnologie nella formazione dei novice driver: Simulatori e guida autonoma. Il contributo di SIMUSAFE
C. POLEDDI
Presidente Associazione Italiana Professionisti per la Sicurezza Stradale

Ore 12.30
La sanzione ha un ruolo nella formazione dei neopatentati?
P. CESTRA
TSPCK - European Traffic Police Network

Ore 13.00
Esperienza VS Expertise
M.R. CECERI
Direttore Unità di Ricerca Psicologia del Traffico, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

Ore 14.30-16.00
Tavola rotonda Moderata da EMILIO PATELLA
Segretario Nazionale UNASCA

Workshop internazionale

Martedì 26 giugno 2018
Aula Pio XI
Largo A. Gemelli, 1 - Milano

DEPARTMENT OF PSYCHOLOGY

Are novice drivers at risk?

Graduated driving license, a challenge for safety

Earning the driving license is a milestone for the individual's autonomy. Nonetheless data about crashes pinpoint that novice drivers (aged 18-25) are mostly challenged when they start driving, since their skills are tested in real and different driving contexts. For this reason, some countries have adopted the graduated driving license model, so as to verify the driver's ability and compliance to norms before providing her/him with a permanent license. Aim of the workshop is to explore this issue from an international point of view, examining the formative balance and the consequences on personal and public safety.

Ore 09.30
Welcome

Ore 10.00
Preventive interventions for novice drivers according to the Italian law
S. DONDOLINI
Director, Department of Motor Vehicles, Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport

Ore 10.20
Comparing training procedures for novice drivers in different european countries
M. PICARDI
2President, EFA - European Driving School Association

Ore 10.40
Second phase driver training in Austria Background and evaluation
G. BARIL
Traffic psychologist
Director of the Institute for Traffic Psychology, Austria

Ore 11.00
Graduated driving license as phased process: the SWISS case
V. BORGIO
Driving Instructor, Switzerland
G. GALMARINI
Traffic Psychologist, Switzerland

Ore 11.30
Coffee Break

Ore 12.00
New technologies and novice drivers training: the challenges of simulators and self-driven cars. Simusafe project
C. POLEDDI
President, Associazione Italiana Professionisti per la Sicurezza Stradale

Ore 12.30
Which effect of fines in novice drivers education?
P. CESTRA
TSPCK - European Traffic Police Network

Ore 13.00
Experience VS Expertise
M.R. CECERI
Director, Traffic Psychology Unity Research, UCSC

Ore 14.30 - 16.00
Round table Moderated by EMILIO PATELLA, National Secretary UNASCA

International Workshop

June 26, 2018
Aula Pio XI
Largo Gemelli, 1 - Milano

Related research of interest

Cannabis smoking impairs driving performance on the simulator and real driving: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, crossover trial by Micallef et al. (2018).

This is an article in the May volume of the **Fundamental & Clinical Pharmacology** journal. It is about a recent French research trial examining the effect of cannabis on driving performance under real driving and simulator driving conditions. The trial was a double-blind design where half the cigarettes were dosed with THC and half were not. The effect of the THC on driving behaviour was primarily measured through the incidence of inappropriate lane crossings (ILC).

The study recruited healthy men between the ages of 25 and 35 who had driving experience and were occasional users of cannabis. Prior to the study, the participants were assessed by numerous diagnostic questionnaires as well as multiple physical and psychological exams including drug screening for other drugs excluding marijuana.

Figure 1: Number of inappropriate line crossings (log scale) during the 2h driving period (p10).

Study participants did simulation and real driving tests after smoking the test cigarettes. In the real driving component, subjects had to drive two hours on a motorway at a constant speed and with as little lane changing as possible. The real driving component was done in cars with dual controls; driving instructors sat in the cars and were available to take control if necessary. Under simulator conditions, subjects were instructed to stay in the same lane and keep the speed as constant as possible. The simulated traffic was all programmed to drive faster than the respondents to ensure respondents did not need to make any lane changes.

The researchers found that "...THC intake had a detrimental effect on self-confidence to drive, drowsiness and tiredness on the psychological side. Moreover, driving performance is also significantly impaired, in terms of the capacity of the driver to stay in his/her driving lane, but only in simulation conditions" (p10).

Download the article here:

<https://www.pubfacts.com/detail/29752828/Cannabis-smoking-impairs-driving-performance-on-simulator-and-real-driving-A-randomized-double-blind-placebo-controlled-crossover-trial>